

Execution - data collection (treatment group)

Welcome to the activity on elicitation of context-aware features. This is a controlled experiment and the participation is anonymous.

Execution

Write down a requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task "CREATE A COMMENT" (i.e. "comment an existing post").

Please write your answer here:

Is there still time? *

Choose one of the following answers
Please choose only one of the following:

- YES!
- No, time is over.

Write down another requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task "CREATE A COMMENT" (i.e. "comment an existing post").

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'YES!' at question '2 [ISTHERETIME1]' (Is there still time?)

Please write your answer here:

Is there still time? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'YES!' at question '2 [ISTHERETIME1]' (Is there still time?)

Choose one of the following answers
Please choose only one of the following:

- YES!
- No, time is over.

Write down another requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task "CREATE A COMMENT" (i.e. "comment an existing post").

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'YES!' at question '4 [ISTHERETIME2]' (Is there still time?)

Please write your answer here:

Is there still time? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'YES!' at question '4 [ISTHERETIME2]' (Is there still time?)

Choose one of the following answers
Please choose only one of the following:

- YES!
- No, time is over.